

Witchcraft and the Democratization of South Africa

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A. Introduction

The second wind of change, the democratic renewal in Africa and elsewhere in the early 1990th was greeted with great enthusiasm. In South Africa it gave rise to additional expectations as it was linked to liberation from the Apartheid regime. But as years went on without tangible improvement in the social and economic setting of the majority of the population, quite a few of the stakeholders started to view efforts promoted in the name of "democratization" rather as the devil's work or witchcraft, a pretext and hidden agenda, aimed at exploiting innocent citizens (cf. Comaroff 1999). Democratization without development meant next to nothing to them. Bewildered peasants, unemployed, and even striving African entrepreneurs nowadays often trust more in development by means of magic or *muti*, or they resort to extra-legal individual and group violence to make their ends meet, rather than to rely on the state and development assistance by governmental or non-governmental development organizations. In the following chapters, however, we shall not focus on general expectations and connotations of the stakeholders which might obscure Western concepts of democratization or development, but instead on specific aspects of a deep-rooted socio-cultural heritage of African societies, the belief in magic and witchcraft and its articulation with the ongoing process of democratization and development in South Africa. This focus seems to be justified in view of the gravity of social and political problems caused by the spread of witchcraft related violence in recent years, recognized as a national priority crime in 1999, as documented by various Commissions of Inquiries, scholarly analysis (cf. bibliography), and the National Conference on Witchcraft Violence, convened by the Commission on Gender Equality (CGE) in Northern Province in September 1998.

Witchcraft related violence, however, is just the tip of an iceberg, an indicator of a problem by far more profound and of ambiguous qualities which calls for a solution, as we shall explain in detail below. In order to avoid ethnocentric misconceptions right from the beginning, we want to stress that many aspects of this problem are not restricted to South Africa or other African societies, despite undisputable regional differences in incidence, contents, and relevance. Even in the U.S.A. the belief in witchcraft was officially recognized as religion by the High Court in 1982 under the heading of Wicca, which is far from being traditional minded, propagates its objectives with the help of modern concepts and technology, and even owns its website. The revival of occult belief systems around the word has different sources which call for comparative in-depth investigations by future research.

B. Analysis of Problems and Potentials, Open Questions, and Working-Hypotheses

The international discourse on the meaning of magic and witchcraft in Africa is highly controversial, not just between Western and African experts, or between experts and stakeholders, but between antagonistic schools of thought within Western social science alike, as the change in the European conception of African magic over time demonstrated (cf. Pels 1998). The dispute is as least as much about facts and figures, as about values, the question of legitimacy and appropriateness of objectives and concepts, agendas hiding behind research ethics, ethnocentrism and indigenous knowledge, scientific objectivism defending its stand against cultural relativism, biased interpretations of empirical findings based on different methodologies to analyze the problem (cf. Geschiere 1997; Dettmar 1999). This applies very much for the discussion of magic and witchcraft in South Africa too. But here we may profit from a detailed problem analysis, reflecting the emic view of the very stakeholders themselves. The National Conference on Witchcraft Violence stimulated representatives from relevant stakeholder-groups to share their views on witchcraft, to draft a logical framework for problem analysis as well as recommendations to resolve the problem (CGE, 1999:49-67). In summary, the CGE recommended a comprehensive model for the prevention of witchcraft violence by combined activities in the educational, legal, spiritual, community and mental health sectors (CGE, 1999:49, Table 1).

1. Witchcraft in Africa is by no means an exotic phenomenon, restricted to a few remote places, but an integral part of day to day life in most African societies.

The belief in magic and witchcraft is widespread in Africa since immemorial times. It did not vanish with the advent of "European civilization", introduced by the colonial powers under the cover of "moral education of the natives", to justify their ruthless exploitation. Missionary zeal and development aid, meant to push the process of modernization, did not have a great effect either. According to many Africans who believe in it, both the incidence and virility of black magic or witchcraft have significantly increased throughout sub-Saharan Africa in the past decades, in rural and urban areas alike. International research agrees that these occult belief systems are by no means an exotic phenomenon, restricted to a few remote places, but an integral part of day to day life in most African societies (cf. Geschiere 1997; Kohnert 1997, for a review of literature). Quite often witchcraft accusations are promoted not just by individual kinship conflicts, but by social stress and strain, caused by the modernization-process in general, and accentuated by the commoditization of social relations and its "fetishization" in particular (cf. Nadel 1952; Kohnert 1983).

This holds for South Africa too (cf. bibliography). A recent problem analysis by representatives of the South African Human Rights Commission (HRC) declared that the "belief in witchcraft has the capacity to paralyze people" and identified witchcraft violence as "a sign of a pathology in a community". Representatives of the Department of Constitutional Development declared witchcraft violence as "the number-one enemy of our society", and the Department of Justice deplored among others its "negative effects on the economy of the country" (CGE, 1999:55). However, in the past, neither the state, nor liberation movements, political parties, or trade unions seemed to have cared very much about it. Only when social and political conflict boiled over to a veritable witch craze, as happened in the past decade in Northern Province, KwaZulu-Natal, Eastern Cape (cf. Ralushai 1996; Niehaus 1993; 1995; Minaar et al. 1991; Delius 1997; Evans 1992; Kessel 1993) or in overcrowded townships like Soweto (cf. Ashfort 1998), it deemed necessary to take notice officially. There is a growing awareness that current legislation, like the Witchcraft Act of 1957, still reflecting colonial reasoning, is unable to cope with the problem. By its salomonic phrasing it

punishes both the alleged witch and the allegedly bewitched, i. e. those who express their fear by witchcraft accusations. It thus protects the real culprits, at least from the perspective of people believing in the existence of witchcraft. Therefore, the state has been challenged, by both independent bodies and political parties like the ANC, to "review the legal system from being Eurocentric to reflecting the reality of a multicultural nation" (CGE, 1999:55). Therefore, the CGE, the Department of Justice, and the Law Commission of South Africa have set up a committee to draw up proposals for a new law. In February 2000 it presented parliament with a first draft of the "Regulation of Baloyi Practices Act", *Baloyi* being the more precise Venda terminus for socio-cultural practices, which could loosely translated by the English word "witchcraft" (cf. ANC-news 14.02.00).

Without state intervention considered to be legitimate, that is left on their own, the concerned hitherto looked for help in the informal sector, or engaged in self-justice. This has contributed to a rapid erosion of the state's monopoly on force, which seriously affected legitimacy of public institutions. Even traditional authorities, formerly considered to be the guardians of customary law, are now at pains to cope with the situation, because of considerable changes in the incidence, content, and form of witchcraft accusations over time, and the compromising attitude of traditional authorities during the Apartheid regime. African independent and pentecostal churches, mushrooming all over Africa, as well as "modern" witch-finders, like leaders of political motivated ANC-youth organizations, have emphatically offered to cater more effectively about the felt needs of the people than either the state or traditional leaders. But it is open to question, whether institutions or personalities belonging to the informal sector, are always likely to act in the best interest of society.

2. The belief in witchcraft exerts a great seducing power over many Africans, regardless of religion, education or social status.

Regardless of religious orientation, education, gender, and social status, the witch-belief has profound impact on day to day decision-making of many Africans in general, and on politics and the moral economy of African societies in particular (cf. Geschiere 1997:1-25; Comaroff et al. 1993; 1998; Ritchken 1994). To the believer it provides a universe of deep affections, a life-belt in the troubled waters of general insecurity, enhanced by the African prebend economy, lack of transparency and accountability on all levels of economy and society: comfort and excitement, superior knowledge and power, but as well deadly fear, anguish, fury or outraged revenge form part of the emotional fabric underlying the belief in witchcraft, depending on the situation. Unfortunately, positive sensations are by far outnumbered by negative ones, at least concerning its virulence. Although witchcraft belief is deeply rooted in African traditions and custom, it is overwhelmingly characterized as destructive, destabilizing and evil, even by traditional leaders in South Africa (CGE, 1999:49-55). Its seducing force the belief in magic and witchcraft derives from two major sources: firstly, from the thrill that supernatural power and potency or the unlimited pursuit of selfish passion and greed, ascribed to the witch by the envious believer, exerts on him, confronting him at the same time with his own impotency vis à vis these occult forces. Secondly, by explaining in a causal manner the singularity of accidental events, which cannot be explained by scientific proof. In fact, by its very nature the occult evades inter-subjective control on the part of the believer, like any religion would. Thus witchcraft beliefs satisfy a deeply seated desire for certainty that the world is concerned with us and our fate, and nothing happens just by chance. The admission of a province of life where malevolent forces, like a witch, can be discovered and attacked makes it possible to bear a universe devoid of such design (cf. Nadel

1952). Apparently this holds even for the African elite, i. e. quite a number of decision-makers in politics, economy, and society at large (cf. Geschiere 1997; 1996; Kohnert 1996; Ralushai 1996).

3. The belief in magic and witchcraft is highly ambiguous, both in contents and in its effects.

The underlying causes of witch-belief, its historical roots, as well as the effects may differ significantly according to social strata and modes of production in which it is embedded (cf. Austen 1993; Ardener 1970; Geschiere 1997:146-151; Hunter-Wilson 1951; Kohnert 1983). Quite often it has been instrumentalized, by conservative and radical African leaders alike (e. g. Eyadéma, Moboutu, Kérékou, or liberation movements in Guinea-Bissau, Mosambic, Zimbabwe etc.), to make their ends meet, e. g. by mystifying exploitation or by eliminating opponents, usually without any regard to the disintegrating long-term effects on society. But also grass-root liberation movements throughout Africa have been seen to use witchcraft accusations as "cults of counterviolence" (Wilson 1992) against political enemies, often under the pretext of combating "the relics of feudalism" (e. g. the "comrades" in Gogoza, in the border region of Transkei/Natal; cf. Evans 1992:56, or politically motivated witch-hunt in Marxist-Leninist Benin under Kérékou), in the fight against colonialism or apartheid (e. g. witchcraft accusations against leaders of the National Party in SA; cf. Childester, 1992:43-66,151-52), or to enhance their own legitimacy *vis-à-vis* traditional authorities, as leaders of youth organizations in Southern KwaZulu (cf. Evans, 1992) or Lebowa, South Africa (Kessel, 1993; Niehaus, 1993; Ritchken 1988). The concerned population might see in these witch-hunters even heroes who cleanse their areas of evil, rather than to view them as the evil itself. Thus, under certain historical conditions, witch-hunts constitute what Peter Geschiere (1996; 1997), quoting D. C. Martin, called a "popular mode of political action", directed to promote the dawn of a new democratic order, to equalize the income and wealth distribution, or to defend the ideal of solidarity within acephalous village communities.

There is still a lot of confusion in international academic discussion about the apparently contradictory political functions of occult belief systems and their underlying rationale. Therefore, causes and effects of witchcraft movements are difficult to predict. A thorough empirical investigation into the articulation of witchcraft beliefs with the process of democratization and economic development could probably clear the debate of some of these contradictions.

4. The poor and vulnerable suffer most from witch-hunts. This may have profound implications for democratization and poverty alleviation projects.

In general, the most vulnerable, the poor and deprived, elderly women and disabled, suffer most from witchcraft accusations (Ralushai 1996; CGE, 1999: 49-60). This may have far reaching implications for the process of democratization, efforts to decentralize, or the promotion of poverty alleviation programs (CGE, 1999:49). These programs usually intervene into existing social structures of a target population, hampered by conflicts between different strata, ethnic or religious groups, young and old, male and female. As a rule, the benefits of modernization will not be distributed equally, but instead favour some while disfavours others. Development projects, constituting arenas of strategic groups in their struggle for power and control over project resources, are likely to add further social stress to an already endangered precarious balance of power, providing an ideal background against which witchcraft accusations may flourish (cf. Bierschenk et al 1993:97-106). Examples for the interference of witchcraft belief with democratization or development planning in Africa abound for those who want to see (cf. Geschiere 1997:4-6; 1996; Kohnert 1996:1351-54). But unfortunately most development experts and politicians, the majority of which still being interested rather in the transfer of capital, technology and Western concepts

than in improved human relations, the ultimate aim of development cooperation, are reluctant to recognize the problem.

5. To challenge the negative effects of occult belief systems, we may have to concentrate more on investigation into the question of emotions than on rationality.

In general, Western educated experts, European and African alike, consider witchcraft basically as an "illogic and mistaken belief" which should be eradicated as soon as possible by education and critical assessment (CGE, 1999:49,53). Methodologically, however, the difference in the rationality of African witchcraft beliefs and Western forms of reasoning lies more with the degree of its "reduction of complexity", to borrow an expression of Niclas Luhman, than with the degree of rationality: "Zande belief in witchcraft in no way contradicts empirical knowledge of cause and effect. The world known to the senses is just as real to them as it is to us ... They are foreshortening the chain of events, and in a particular social situation are selecting the cause that is socially relevant and neglecting the rest." (Thus) "witchcraft explains *why* events are harmful to man and not *how* they happen." (cf. Evans-Pritchard 1976:24-25; italics of the author).

If particular manners of reduction of complexity, and not different rationalities are the major distinction between African magic and Western rational reasoning, then Western educated scientists, experts, and politicians should be especially careful not to cultivate the hybris of rationality in their dialog with African stakeholders. "Irrational behavior" because of methodologically unsound reduction of complexity is common in Western societies too. It may suffice to quote just one example: Increasing privatization and commercialization of social relations as characteristic feature of globalized capitalism favored the intrusion into the privacy of individual consumers or employees. The delusion of being able to discover the essence of human beings, the *homunculus* of the true self, by simply reducing its complexity to qualifications and needs, which could be detected by technical means and then be used for commercial exploitation, e. g. by polygraphic analyses and close circuit television of individual employees, by user-profiles of consumers etc., has lead to serious distortions in individual and social rationality, the continued attack on privacy by the private sector (cf. Duclos 1999). The obsession to isolate and fix the "true" ideas and emotions of human beings by technical investigation must, however, inevitably fail, as it is based on a methodological fallacy. Our conception of both human nature and scientific objectivity in general, can not be isolated and fixed by science once and for all, as both depend on the unremitting evolution of knowledge, the possibility of mutual exchange and critique, and last not least, on actual social conventions and social structures encouraging or averting critical reflection of our present knowledge (cf. Popper, 1972:112). The latter is decisive in setting the limits between legitimate critical discourse on the one hand, and dogmatic pursuit of "enemies to society" or witch-hunts on the other. Thus, we revert to the central theme of our argument: the open society and its enemies, to borrow a phrase by Karl R. Popper, the nestor of neo-positivist philosophy. The given socio-cultural setting and the social structure have become the cornerstones of Western delimitation of objectivity and rationality, just as the denunciation of persons as witches by their fellow citizens depends finally, at least according to the classical interpretation of African witchcraft by Evans-Pritchard (as quoted above), on the social recognition of certain worldviews on cause and effect.

Although Evans-Pritchard was right in confronting common Western prejudices of the 1920th on primitive African thinking with the intrinsic logic of the belief in magic and witchcraft, this was just the half of the truth. As illustrated by recent research in neuro-physiology (cf Damasio 1994); he

was probably wrong in underestimating the profound structural links between emotion and rational reasoning in human beings in general. Rational behavior is influenced by deep seated emotions at least as much as by empirical knowledge. In fact, man can not act rationally without moving emotions. In contrast to the Cartesian postulate on the fundamental separation of body and soul, human decision making, by its very biological structure, is never determined by rational reasoning alone, but guided by emotions grown on, and deeply embedded in the respective culture of the actor (Damasio, 1994:325-328). One may go even one step further in discussing the relevance of Gerald Edelmans' (1992:232-236) hypothesis that the biological self, at least vital parts of the human brain, have been conditioned and structured in the course of human genesis by basic values needed for survival; thus, evolution of mankind provided for the acceptance of basic human value-systems guiding its actions; possibly Edelman's thesis even sheds new light on the controversy concerning the existence of universal human rights. According to recent neuro-physiological theories on cognition, the perception of the world in the human brain has been directed through the filter of positive and negative sentiments from the very birth on. There exists a close neuro-biological link between feeling and thinking, which makes the existence of emotions (based on the respective socio-cultural setting), a precondition for any rational action, either of Africans or of Europeans. But what would be even more important in this context, the linkage of ratio and emotions, born out and developed within specific socio-cultural settings (cf. Damasio 1994:327), is of immediate relevance for the resolution of pressing social and political problems mentioned above, such as education or the propensity to violent mob actions against witches.

Now, occult belief systems, like religions in general, induce not just a certain vision of the world and of human relations, but they provide, as shown above, for strong emotions as well. This concerns not just individual hate, fear, or other emotions directly linked to witchcraft, but to the whole fabric of the human emotional system, as indicated above. The state, NGOs or other progressive institutions of civil society would literally deprive the concerned of their capability for survival, if they would deny them categorically their belief in magic and witchcraft, without providing, jointly within the framework of educational programs and a gradual scientific dismantling of witchcraft belief (as advocated by the CGE and other institutions), a convincing source of equally strong alternative "development-enhancing" emotions. No wonder that most education programs which concentrated on rational reasoning, have utterly failed since the beginning of colonial rule, be it by missionaries, schools or the state.

6. There still exists considerable confusion in science and politics about how public institutions should deal with witchcraft.

Since 1994, the new democratic government of South Africa, political parties, and trade unions alike, have been under increasing pressure to take account of witchcraft beliefs, not just to prevent further loss of lives and property, but in order to combat the loss of their legitimacy as well. However, in actual practice, government, community leaders, representatives of civil society, and the concerned differ widely on how to deal with witchcraft. In September 1998 the National Conference on Witchcraft, organized by the Commission of Gender Equality in the Northern Province, pushed government to change its attitude towards witchcraft. Its representatives conceded an urgent need for developing new strategies which should not simply deny the existence of witchcraft, especially since this approach has utterly failed to work in the past. Besides educational and legal tasks, namely educational programs and the revision of the anti-witchcraft act, the experts favored among others, spiritual alternatives, substitution of witchcraft violence by spiritual healing, and "activities to treat the communities psychosocial needs." (CGE, 1999:49).

In addition, modern and traditional rulers alike have to be aware of and understand the language of ritual violence, and act accordingly, if they want to guarantee anything near to a state-monopoly of violence as a necessary, but not sufficient pre-condition for legitimate rule and democratization. The call of grass-root organizations, politicians and academics for an indigenization of national laws and regulations, i. e. its adaptation to the African socio-cultural setting in general, and the official recognition of the existence of witchcraft in particular, might be justified, but only in as far as basic human rights are respected. Any attempt for a "domestication" of witch-belief, e. g. by an opportunist indigenization of legislation, notably by the repeal of the anti-witchcraft laws of 1957, official recognition of witchcraft and accusers, without due regard to universal concepts of human rights, is hardly to be considered as sustainable. It could perhaps help to regain credibility and legitimacy of the state in the short run, but it may even promote the witch craze, accentuate social cleavages in the long run, or lead to despotism of charismatic rulers in the long run.

7. Research in democratization "from below" could favor not just transparency, democracy, and development, but the "domestication" of witchcraft belief as well.

In view of the importance of an open society as precondition of democratization in general and rational handling of the witchcraft problem in particular (cf. above), isolated measures would hardly deliver tangible results in allaying the growing fear of witchcraft within the population. This applies within the realm of legislation or jurisdiction, and for state or party sponsored public education campaigns in human rights as well. Attempts of the ANC in Lebowa in the late 1980s to combat the witchcraft belief of its followers by crash courses in scientific socialism utterly failed, which was not surprising in view of decades of failed similar "top-down" modernization campaigns of the extension service elsewhere in Africa. Therefore, we should investigate into new participatory forms of dialogue, more adapted to the socio-cultural setting. The present discussion on African forms of democracy, relying more on the communal nature of African societies and different perceptions of participation in the political process (cf. Thiel et al 2000) may contribute to solving the problem, especially by showing the alternatives to Western style participation in party politics which promote competitive and often conflictual relations with fellow citizens.

However, to develop grass-root democracy and transparency might prove to be a difficult task concerning the combat of witchcraft violence, in view of general fear and insecurity surrounding the discussion of witchcraft, at least in the beginning; but as well, because the ethics of the craft of traditional healers, *sangomas* or witchcraft cults are detrimental to equality, transparency, and accountability, three basic conditions of both a rewarding dialogue and the development of democratic attitudes. But in the long run, the promotion of transparency and the democratization of decision-making processes, on all levels, in politics as well as in society and economy, might be rewarding. Not just because it would favor the process of democratization and development in general, but as it would most likely contribute to the gradual eradication of witchcraft-accusations too. Where there is transparency, insight into the motives of your neighbor, relative, or political rival, and where social structure provides for more equal access to resources, there is less need to blame scapegoats for individual misfortune.

In view of the apparent contradictions between competing witchcraft theories (cf. Geschiere 1995), however, more research is required into the specific roots of actual witchcraft accusations and their relation with the social, economic and political environment. Backed by corresponding research, concerted actions of the state, political parties, the "civics" and the concerned could be

developed to promote simultaneously the insight in underlying causes of witchcraft accusations, reconciliation as well as democratization and development "from below".

Instructions or public extension- and training programs "from above" aimed at eradicating the witchcraft belief are hardly convincing for the concerned. They might on the contrary, even reinforce the already existing emotional resentment against the state or other public or "foreign" political institutions. What would be required are new participatory structures of communication and decision making between the state and its citizens, between the political and economic elite and the deprived, between research project personnel and the stakeholders, in order to establish a dialogue based on mutual trust and understanding. The latter is considered to be a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for an effective promotion of alternative concepts of world vision, values and emotions compatible with a respect for universal human rights and a social dimension of adjustment. The technical dialogue on rationality would have to be accompanied and supported by a dialogue on values, emotions and human relations. Obviously, state administration on its own would be totally overstretched with this task. Instead, this would be the genuine task of non-governmental- and civil-society organizations (NGOs, and "civics"), backed by sound scientific research. Promising methods of dialogue have been developed recently within the field of development cooperation in Western Africa recently, such as local drama performance, transfer of extension "messages" by *griots* and traditional dancing masques. Such communicative strategies could be tested and adapted to the specific requirements of participatory analysis in collaboration with the concerned in South Africa as well.

8. Participatory analyses of the rich potential of African cultures might help to adapt structures of communication to the requirements of conflict resolution and development.

Social science could contribute significantly to attain this common aim, e. g. by a participatory analysis of the problems caused by witchcraft belief, as well as of the potentials which a rich and vivid African culture may offer for their solution. Thus current hypotheses, offered by some African politicians during the National Witchcraft Conference in the Northern Province in Sept. 1998 on the possibility to safeguard witchcraft-beliefs by "purification" and transformation should be tested for its empirical viability as well (although to us, this does not seem to be a sustainable solution). Scientific research into the rich body of oral history of local communities may help to discover new channels of communication, modes of reconciliation, healing, and reintegration of victims of witchcraft accusations. Finally, research could clarify the apparent contradictions between different ambiguous aspects and effects of occult belief systems as indicated above.

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